

TEACHING DEMOCRACY AND ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP THROUGH CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION: HOW DO WE KNOW IT WORKS?

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Abstract

Citizenship education, i.e. activities aimed to teach citizens of recipient countries basic values, knowledge, and skills how to be an active and engaged citizen, has become a popular form of empowering young people within democracy assistance of young democracies from Visegrad countries. This paper outlines some of the programs aimed at educating and activating young people in Eastern Europe to be more socially responsible for their local community, region, and country, and focuses on impact evaluation of these programs. Different methods used to evaluate the impact of the citizenship education programs are being presented and discussed together with their advantages and limitations. These suggestions can be useful for both practitioners wishing to learn whether their citizenship education programs produce impact, as well as for researchers wanting to answer the question whether and how citizenship education efforts of organizations from Visegrad countries influence young people.

Keywords: citizenship education; active citizenship; youth participation; youth empowerment

Funding: This work was supported by National Science Centre (NCN) Poland [grant number UMO-2013/09/D/HS5/04381]. Special thanks to the members of the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) „Citizenship“ standing group for the inspiration and comments on my work, and Aleksandra Galus of her work on the research project. Many thanks also to a partner organization and a donor for their collaboration—without that I would not be able to implement my research ideas.

INTRODUCTION

Citizenship education becomes an important sphere outside the school educational system. We find that many of the projects implemented by the young democracies from Visegrad group take a form of citizenship education as a form of sharing their experience with democracy. The goal of these programs is to encourage young people to become aware and active citizens, and ready to take actions in their close community, region, and the country. These educational programs have a potential to be important part of youth empowerment

mechanism, however there is lack of evidence whether they make a difference. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to provide discuss how organizations and researchers can measure the impact of citizenship education programs.

If we want to provide rigorous evidence we need to employ a rigorous methodology. We also need to boil down the evaluation to specific program and test the impact of this program on its beneficiaries. An impact evaluation can answer the question of whether a program works. This means we need to examine how the people who participated in the program performed compared to how they would have performed if they had not had a chance to participate in the program. We can never know what would have happened in the absence of the program, but we can use different evaluation techniques in attempt to make comparisons.

In this paper, I provide some suggestions on how we can go about measuring the impact of the citizenship education program. These suggestions are drawn on the practical experience with one of the NGOs I have a privilege to work with. The inspiration for the impact evolution methodology comes from the Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab (J-PAL).

1. UNDERSTANDING CITIZENSHIP, ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP, AND CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION

Citizenship is often defined as the rights and duties relating to an individual's belonging to the political community. It implies some integration into a national community and common heritage. However the definition of citizenship was subject to many challenges and thus evolutions. Each time when the community becomes a place where it is difficult to live it—let it be war or autocratic regime—and people demand the redefinition of citizenship rights, the concept of citizenship is challenged (Barnett and Low 2004). The promotion of democracy and human rights by international organizations and associations, as well as globalization process expanded the definition of citizenship to include some universal rights. In times of globalization the definition of citizenship evolved and seems to be separated from the strong identification with the nation-state. This of course does not mean that such people living in a given country want to waive their nationality, but rather that such identity becomes secondary.

The citizenship also becomes to denote not only rights and obligations, but also how individuals behave on everyday bases, what activities they are engaged in, and how they relate themselves to the smaller (city, town, village) and broader community (e.g. global community). In other words, participation became to be perceived as an important element of citizenship. Hence “active citizenship” has been used to refer to people who feel responsible for the community, who feel potential to make a change, who are ready to take action and who get involved in local communities (Crick and Lockyer 2010). There is no active citizenship without participation, but is not restricted to political participation only. As various efforts of scholars and practitioners to measure active citizenship for democracy show, active citizenship is understood as participation in civil society, community and/or in political life (De Weerd et al.2005; Ogris and Westphal 2005; Abs and Veldhuis 2006; Hoskins 2006). Democracy in principle demands that citizens participate, thus active citizenship and democracy are closely related and one cannot exist without another.

Just like definition of citizenship has changed, also the theory and practice related to citizenship education evolved. Commonly, the term citizenship education has been associated with a subject at schools (Solhaug 2013) that aims to provide knowledge about political concepts,

political processes and institutions at various governmental levels, as well as to increase understanding of citizens' engagement in decision-making process. Remarkable efforts to rethink civic education might be seen in last ten to fifteen years. Much attention has been paid to citizenship education in terms of evaluation and improvement of school-based education aimed at developing democratic knowledge and skills (Campbell, 2007; Campbell, 2008; Lawy and Biesta, 2009; Martens, 2012; Veugelers, 2011). After reviewing the classical literature on democratic citizenship (e.g. Almond and Verba, 1963; Biesta, Lawy, and Kelly, 2009), Print (2013) presents five dimensions of active citizen: knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and intended behaviour/dispositions, which may constitute an integrated approach to civic education. Print and Lange (2012) and Print (2013) recognize those dimensions as the basis for education and enhancing civic competences within schools through the formal but also informal school curriculum.

However, the need to improve youth' engagement in decision-making process through developing skills of critical thinking, debating, and undertaking civic and political activities by young people and encouraging them to actively participate and instil democratic values, challenged citizenship education as a subject at schools (Mycock and Tonge, 2014). According to Himmelmann (2013, p. 3), we can observe: *"a new and specified form of 'democratic citizenship education' beyond just civics; for a new way of 'teaching democracy' beyond teaching institutional political settings or a new 'education of, for and through democracy' beyond mere teacher-centered instruction in politics."*

Thus, citizenship education that includes educational efforts in order to strengthen democracy and qualify citizens for participation, has become not only the domain of schools and national educational systems, but also other actors who engage in this field. The need for educating young people for being more active citizens seem to be more and more popular approach among non-governmental organizations both domestic and international (Schulz, 2008; UNESCO, 2014). Citizenship education seems to be interrelated with empowering youth and building well-functioning and strong civil society (Maroshek-Klarman 1996). It is believed that NGOs citizenship education' projects are part of youth empowerment mechanism aimed at increasing youth participation in civic life.

However, we still have little knowledge about the direct and indirect role that citizenship education plays in activating young people (Biesta, 2011; Galston, 2001; Lawy and Biesta, 2009). Moreover, little is known whether and how citizens can be educated about the idea of responsible citizenship and participation outside educational system and whether and how important role can play non-governmental organizations in this process. Therefore in my study, I aim to fill this gap by studying citizenship education efforts of non-governmental organizations, especially from other countries. I believe that NGOs from young democracies have unique perspectives and approach to teach and promote democratic values. In this short paper, I would like to present briefly these efforts to influence young people, and since my aim is also to evaluate these efforts, I would like to discuss possible methods of evaluating citizenship education programs.

2. SHARING THE EXPERIENCE WITH DEMOCRACY THROUGH CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION PROGRAMS

Believing that active citizenship starts with education, many youth projects initiated and organized by the NGOs from Visegrad countries in other countries in the region, take a form

of citizenship education programs. The NGOs experiences undoubtedly also shaped their view on how other countries should be assisted in their struggle to democracy. They played an important role during the democratic transition and where recipients of aid themselves, which helped them develop a unique form of passing their experience and a good example to other countries (Pospieszna 2014). Citizenship education undoubtedly is one of the ways to share the experience with democratic transition.

What does citizenship education mean for the NGO? For them it is a fieldwork, where they are trying to put the young people in the environment that is very different from that at school and at home, *i.e.* take part in activities aimed to teach them basic values, knowledge, and skills relating to democracy. Citizenship education is practiced through activities organized in the partner countries, such as providing didactic materials to schools, organizing workshops, discussions and knowledge contests. The bulk of citizenship education programs, however, is implemented outside the partner country and takes the form of: summer schools, internships, scholarships, exchange programs, and study missions programs.

Within my research project, I work with the NGOs that every year invites over 200 students from Belarus, Moldova, Ukraine and the Russian Federation to come for a two-week visit. The aim of the program is provide an incentive for the students to actively participate in public life and become aware citizens. The program is based on informal education methods—the organization creates environment in which the youngsters can experience democratic values. Students can meet with governmental officials, local authorities; they visit various public institutions, media outlets, and companies. The participants also meet with students at the universities and with representatives of student associations, as well as with representatives of non-governmental organizations. They have a chance to ask question, but more important to take parts in debates during which they can experience different opinions and attitudes.

Young people have a great potential to play important role in a society and that in order to boost their participation youth empowerment mechanism is required, which might not be created from within the country, just like in an authoritarian state like Belarus. Therefore participation in such educational program may build young people' sense of power that they are able to make changes in their communities they belong to, region and even their country. However, the questions I am trying to answer in my research are: How can measure impact of this intervention, and how can we be sure that the changes we observe in the participants can be attributed to the program?

3. MEASURING THE IMPACT OF THE CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION PROGRAMS ON YOUNG PEOPLE

We have a clearly defined program, with a clear goal, and we want to know if this specific program as a whole works. How can we go about finding this out? Below I discuss the advantage and limitations of some of the most common impact evaluation methods that can be employed.

Before-and-after comparisons

This method measures how program participants improved or changed as the result of their participation in the program. The outcomes of the participants are recorded before the program is implemented and these are then compared to the outcomes of these same participants

after the program ends. We have to collect data on the outcomes of program participants before and after the program is implemented. This can be done through surveys conducted before and after the program. For example, the organization I am working with runs survey among the participants before the program in order to measure their knowledge, opinions, attitudes regarding the role of the citizens in the society, the role of government, the attitudes toward the European Union and the like, and then the same set of questions is being asked in the post survey.

This methodology allows comparing the outcomes before and after, and if the scores are higher than they were before the program started, it seems that the program has made a difference. Is the before-and-after comparison the right methodology for evaluating the program then? The methodology seems to be simple, but questionable whether we can be sure whether the change in scores can be attributed to program intervention, or whether something else caused scores to rise. If we simply measure knowledge and perceptions before and after the programs, we cannot be certain whether some or all of the improvement was due to the many other things that changed and influenced the learning of the young people during the same time.

The greatest limitation of the methodology is that we assume that the program was the only factor influencing any changes in the measured outcome over time, however, many other factors other than the program we are evaluating can change the outcomes of the program over time, especially if the program lasts longer. Especially, if the beneficiaries of the program are young people who, in contrast to adults, develop and change quickly. They can be activated or informed by doing something with their peers, or taking part in other parallel events, or being influenced by parents, teachers. All other factors probably could educate and empower young people even if these young people were not given a chance to participate in the program.

In order to overcome the drawbacks of this methodology we can conduct surveys immediately after the end of the program. Also, this methodology is recommended to evaluate the programs that had short time span—then we can limit the influence of many other factors than a program, which could influence changes. If there is one year or more between pre and post tests than we risk that many factors will have influenced the learning levels of the young people who participated in the program. However, even in short-term programs, we may either underestimate the impact of the program, we might even find no impact; and also we may also overestimate impact by assuming that all the improvements were due to our program.

Participant—nonparticipant comparison

According to this methodology instead of comparing scores before and after participation in the program, we could also compare the scores of those young people who got to the program to those who did not participate in the program. Again we conduct surveys and if we find that there is a difference between for example knowledge, attitudes and interests of participants and non-participants we can attribute this difference to the program.

Although this methodology allows us with the higher confidence to see the difference between what happened with the program with what would have happened without the program, this also methodology has some limitations. Usually those who were recruited to the program are often already different from those who do not. For example, an NGO I am working with in the recruitment procedure already requires from students to be active and

participate in different organizations. The program selects participants based on qualifications and it is quite possible that the young people are already well-motivated and activated and care more about democratic values than those who did not apply. In other words, those who get receive a program are already different from those who did not get a program. This tendency is called a selection. If we fail to account for selection in our impact evaluation, we can introduce selection bias into our estimate of impact. This means that we may risk attributing differences in outcomes to the program when they are actually caused by differences already existed between those selected and non-selected to the program.

An impact evaluation is only as good as the comparison group that can mimic what would have happened in the absence of the program. If the comparison group is not good enough it can ruin the evaluation and make it invalid. Therefore, the way to overcome the problem of preexisting differences in this methodology would be to employ randomized controlled trials discussed below.

Running randomized evaluations

The key feature of a randomized evaluation is that the people who have access to the program are selected randomly. This methodology ensures that there are not systematic differences between participants and non-participants (comparison group), and allows to measure what impacts were caused by the program (Glennester and Takavarasha 2013). The NGO I am working with has already employed this methodology to evaluate its citizenship education program directed toward young people from the Eastern Europe. Randomized evaluations should be designed before the project starts, therefore there were many program-specific issues that we had to discuss in order to match the expectations of the organization, donor, and requirements of this methodology. Hopefully, soon I will be able to present the results of the impact evaluation of the program.

Qualitative methods

The above-presented methods of measuring the impact of citizenship education programs are some quantitative impact evaluations. Of course, there are qualitative methods that are being used by the organizations, such as open-ended interviews with the participants, to investigate the impact of the program. The major difference between qualitative and quantitative methods is that the latter do not attempt to reduce experiences to data. The advantage of this method is that may touch upon the issues that might be discussed in closed-ended survey questions. In other words, we may collect some rich, detailed information, that otherwise would not be collected. The difficulty in applying this method is in the interpretation and analysis of the information collected. Despite the limitations, I found that many organizations implementing citizenship education projects present the stories of the former participants who became important civil activists or even politician in order to demonstrate the impact of their projects. The participants may discuss how the program has impacted them, changed their perceptions, knowledge or even lives, but it requires from the participant to know what would have happened in the absence of the program.

When asking participants how a program changed their lives we asking them to disentangle all the many chances that were going on in society from those that were driven by the participation in the program. This however, still might be difficult. Therefore, this method is good for simply describing a situation, but does not allow drawing conclusions about the impact of the program.

CONCLUSION

Measuring the impact of intervention requires from us to compare what has happened with the intervention with what would have happened without this intervention. If we are interested in evaluating impact of citizenship education we should test the impact at the micro level. I suggest evaluating the citizenship education programs implemented by the organizations inside or outside the country. Many NGOs in Visegrad countries engage in promoting active citizenship among young people through the programs that aim to educate, and to raise awareness and thus to empower young people to be active citizens and advocats of pro-democratic changes.

In this short paper I presented some possible impact evaluation methods based on the experience with partner organization in evaluating the citizenship education program. These are some practical suggestions for the organizations wishing to find out the impact of their programs. However, the impact evaluation methods may allow also researchers to understand better how citizenship education is being practiced through other venues than schools and what the role of NGOs can play in this process.

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NON

ACADEMIC

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